

Studies on the Catalytic Decomposition of H_2O_2 by Hydrous Bismuth Oxide in presence of Electrolytes

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The catalytic decomposition of H_2O_2 by hydrous bismuth oxide has been investigated in the presence of electrolytes and also at various temperatures. The effect of variation of the concentration of the catalyst as well as that of H_2O_2 has also been studied.

It has been found that the decomposition is a true chemical reaction. The catalyst concentration does not seem to have much influence at lower concentrations of H_2O_2 , but enormous increase in the rate of reaction is observed with higher concentrations. It is generally seen that the decrease in catalytic activity is correlated with the increase in the valence of the electrolyte used in accordance with the Hardy-Schulze's law. In all the cases first order constants are obtained except at higher concentrations where second order constants have been obtained. The nature of the curves of the electrolyte effects resemble that of the adsorption isotherm.

The catalytic decomposition of H_2O_2 into water and molecular oxygen was first studied a century ago by Thenard and since then many investigations¹⁻⁸ on the subject have been made which include catalytic decompositions by colloiddally dispersed metals such as Pt and Au, hydrous oxides and the effect of electrolytes etc. But inadequate attention has been paid towards catalytic importance of hydrous oxides in the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide specially with regard to the mechanism involved.

It is, therefore, proposed in this present paper to study the decomposition of H_2O_2 by hydrous bismuth oxide. The decomposition has been studied by varying the concentration of H_2O_2 as well as of the catalyst. The study has also been made with different electrolytes and at different temperatures. The constants e.g., temperature coefficient, energy of activation, change in entropy, free energy of activation and frequency factor have also been calculated.

EXPERIMENTAL

(a) *Materials*.—Potassium chloride, Barium chloride, Potassium dihydrogen phosphate and Potassium permanganate were all of A.R. grade. Disodium hydrogen

1. Bredig and Muller Von Berneck, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1889, 31, 258.
2. Von Euler, *Monatsh.*, 1929, 53, and 54, 1014-22.
3. A Lottermoser, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1929, 35, 610-12.
4. Olcveri and Mandala, *Gazette*, 1930, 60, 878-82.
5. Heath and Walton, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1933, 37, 977-90.
6. A. Kranec, *Przemysl Chem.*, 1955, 11, 291-4.
7. Kazuko, Tarama and Suito, *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1959, 80, 10-13.
8. Veil and Pierron, *Compt. rend.*, 1928, 184, 1028.

phosphate used was of Sterling Co. England, and Potassium sulphate was of S. Merck (pro-analyti). Bismuth nitrate used was of Clarke and Co., Hamberg, Germany. H_2O_2 used for the investigation was of S. Merck.

(b) *Preparation of the catalyst.* Bismuth hydroxide⁹ was precipitated by first dissolving the bismuth nitrate in the smallest possible quantity of dil. HNO_3 and then pouring the solution into an excess of concentrated aqueous ammoniacal solution to avoid the formation of basic salts¹⁰. Then the precipitate was washed on the buchner funnel till it became free from nitrate and hydroxyl ions. At this stage all the precipitates had a tendency to settle with difficulty. The suspension of hydrous bismuth oxide thus obtained was stored in a Pyrex flask.

For bismuth content the suspension was estimated gravimetrically as follows:

The suspension was precipitated by adding a few mls of K_2SO_4 solution, then it was well washed to remove sulphate ions and transferred to a glass sintered crucible. The precipitate was then dried at 150° to convert it into bismuth oxide. Bismuth content was then calculated from bismuth oxide using the relationship $Bi_2O_3 \times 0.8970 = Bi$.

The speed of the reaction was determined by titrating undecomposed H_2O_2 with $KMnO_4$ in presence of dil. H_2SO_4 . The reaction was checked by adding 10 ml of 4 $N H_2SO_4$ in each titration. Only one suspension has been used while taking a particular set of readings in order to ensure constancy of dispersion (cf. Ghosh and Coworkers¹¹).

A known volume of H_2O_2 of the desired strength was taken in a Pyrex conical flask painted with Japan Black. The required volume of the conductivity water was added. Then the electrolyte solutions, when used, were added from the pipettes. Then this conical flask was placed in a thermostat. The second flask containing catalyst was also placed in the same thermostat. When both the flasks attained temperature of the thermostat, the required volume of the catalyst was sucked from the second flask and poured into the first. This order was followed throughout because according to Lottermoser and Lehmann¹², the order of the addition of the constituents is an important factor. 10 ml of the reaction mixture were withdrawn at suitable intervals of time and the residual H_2O_2 was estimated each time by titrating with standard $KMnO_4$.

In all the above observations, duplicate determinations were made in each case.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of temperature: The decomposition was studied at the temperatures of 30° , 40° , 50° under identical conditions. The concentration of the catalyst used was 0.2107 gms Bi/litre, while the final concentration of H_2O_2 was 0.03*N*. A summary of the results

9. M. M. P. Muir and D. Carnegie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1887, 51, 79.

10. P. Thibault, *J. Chim. Pharm.*, 1900, (6), 12, 559; *Bull. Soc. Chim.* 1903, (3) 29, 680.

11. Ghosh and Coworkers, *Kolloid. Z.*, 1953, 132, 143; 1953, 132, 141; 1951, 124, 31.

12. Lottermoser, *Kolloid. Z.*, 1921, 23, 250.

is given in table I where temperature coefficient, energy of activation E , entropy of activation ΔS , frequency factor A and free energy of activation ΔF have been given.

TABLE I

H_2O_2 Conc. 0.03N Temp. range	Temp. Coeff.	E K. Cal.	Temp.	Catalyst Conc. 0.2107 gms Bi/l.			
				Half life in minutes	$A \times 10^{-7}$ Sec ⁻¹	ΔS Cal/°C	ΔF K. Cal.
303° A-313° A	2.36	16.155	303° A	195	4.01	-23.820	23.645
313° A-323° A	2.30	16.700	313° A	82	3.948	-23.915	23.910
303° A-323° A	5.42	16.420	323° A	36	4.344	-23.790	24.170

Effect of catalyst concentration: In order to study the effect of the catalyst concentration, the studies were made by taking six different concentrations of hydrogen peroxide with three different concentrations of the catalyst. The results are summarised in table II.

TABLE II

Conc. of catalyst	Final conc. of H_2O_2	Half life in minutes	Tempera- ture	Average first order constants $k \times 10^6$	Reciprocal of half life
0.1686 gms Bi/l	0.0200 N	58	30°C	198.460	0.01724
	0.0225 N	68	"	169.220	0.01471
	0.0250 N	87	"	133.050	0.01149
	0.0300 N	227	"	50.940	0.00440
	0.0350 N	540	"	21.405	0.00185
	0.0400 N	1130	"	10.106	0.00088
0.2107 gms Bi/l	0.0200 N	36	"	319.500	0.02777
	0.0225 N	41	"	283.770	0.02439
	0.0250 N	47	"	245.300	0.02127
	0.0300 N	69	"	168.070	0.01449
	0.0350 N	129	"	89.790	0.00775
	0.0400 N	191	"	60.488	0.00523
0.2529 gms Bi/l	0.0200 N	34	"	341.520	0.02941
	0.0225 N	36	"	319.500	0.02777
	0.0250 N	38	"	304.830	0.02632
	0.0300 N	44	"	260.570	0.02273
	0.0350 N	78	"	148.0050	0.01282
	0.0400 N	134	"	86.2800	0.00746

From the above table following conclusions could be drawn. As the concentration of the catalyst increases, the half life gradually decreases for all concentrations of H_2O_2 . However, the decrease seems to be more pronounced at higher concentrations of H_2O_2 . If the lowest concentration of the catalyst with the various amounts of H_2O_2 is taken into consideration, then the half life period seems to increase considerably beyond 0.025 N H_2O_2 . But in the case of other two concentrations a similar increase is noticed beyond 0.03 N H_2O_2 .

From the preceding observations it is also clear that at lower concentrations of H_2O_2 , the catalyst concentration does not seem to have much influence, although it affects

the change to a certain extent. This is due to the availability of the surface of the catalyst. But in the case of higher concentrations the influence is much higher than expected and this may be due to the excess surface available for the hydrogen peroxide which comes in contact with the catalyst. This means that any slight increase in the catalyst surface would considerably increase the rate of reaction as is evident at 0.04 N H_2O_2 .

Effect of catalyst concentration on reciprocal of half life period has been calculated and the results are represented in Fig. 1.

It is evident that the reciprocal of half life period is linearly related with increase in concentrations, but in case of lower and higher concentrations this does not seem to hold good. But there is an optimum concentration where it is linearly related. Similar results have been reported by Kepfer and Walton¹³.

Effects of the electrolytes on the catalytic activity. The effect of electrolytes has been studied on the decomposition of H_2O_2 by many colloid chemists¹³⁻¹⁶ and different reasons have been given for the inhibition. Generally, the electrolytes adsorb on the surface of the catalyst, and thus they reduce the surface, therefore, the rate of reaction becomes slow.

In the present case, the dispersed particles of the suspension are positively charged. Therefore, the anions will obviously influence their catalytic activity through neutralisation of their charge. Accordingly the decomposition of H_2O_2 as catalysed by hydrous bismuth oxide has been studied in the presence of KCl , $BaCl_2$, K_2SO_4 , Na_2HPO_4 and KH_2PO_4 at 30° . The catalyst concentration in each case was 0.1686 gms Bi/l. First order constants have been calculated which show better constancy except in the case when the higher concentrations of the mono, bi and trivalent anions of the salts have been used. In the latter case the second order constants have been calculated.

Effect of KCl and $BaCl_2$. In the case of KCl it is seen from the curve in Fig. 2

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

13. Kepfer, R. J. and J. H. Walton, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, **34**, 557-72.

14. Brossa, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1909, **66**, 162.

15. Loevenhart and Kastle, *Am. Chem. J.*, 1903, **29**, 397.

16. Mexted, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 1760.

that there is a gradual decrease in the catalytic activity owing to the adsorption of chloride ions on the surface of the catalyst. This reduces the exposed surface and hence the rate of the decomposition becomes slow.

In the case of $BaCl_2$, we see that it has got much similarity with the graph plotted in the case of KCl . Further, it is seen that on increasing the concentration of electrolyte from 100 to 200 millimoles, there appears sudden increase in the half life of H_2O_2 , which shows that at this concentration almost flocculation of suspension takes place. It has also been observed that the equivalent amount of chloride ions in $BaCl_2$ is less effective than in KCl . It may be owing to the fact that Ba^{++} ions¹⁷ promote the activity of the catalyst; therefore, the promoting effect of Ba^{++} ions somewhat compensates the blocking effect of the chloride ions.

Effect of K_2SO_4 : It is observed from the curve in Fig. 3 that there is an abrupt decrease in the catalytic activity on increasing the electrolyte concentration from 0.01 millimole to 0.05 millimole and after this concentration there is a gradual decrease in the catalytic activity upto 2.0 millimoles. From the above it is concluded that in the region of 0.01-0.05 millimoles concentration, the flocculation of suspension takes place. During this period the particles of the suspension flocculate to form larger particles and thus tend to reduce the exposed surface of the catalyst. Therefore, it causes a great decrease in the catalytic activity. Since the suspension has been flocculated, additions of electrolyte upto 2.0 millimoles do not show any appreciable effect. However, on increasing the concentration beyond 2.0 millimoles the half life again decreases and a dip is observed in the curve. This may presumably be due to charge reversal. But on further increasing the concentration beyond 5.0 millimoles it gets flocculated and the half life again increases.

Effect of Na_2HPO_4 : The curve obtained with trivalent PO_4^{3-} ion as given in Fig. 4 seems to be quite different from the curves obtained by mono and bivalent anions. It is analogous to an adsorption isotherm. In the beginning, the addition of phosphate ions does not have much effect on the catalytic activity. But on increasing the concentration

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

from 0.017 to 0.05 millimole a great decrease in the catalytic activity is observed. In this region two abrupt breaks in the figure have also been observed. This can be explained on the basis that phosphate ions have got stabilising effect¹⁸ on H_2O_2 , e.g., orthophosphoric acid, although being weak acid is a good preservative for H_2O_2 . Quiesser¹⁹ has mentioned that the mixture of salicylic acid and Na_2HPO_4 acts as a preservative for H_2O_2 . Gabler and Menzel²⁰ have shown that Na_2HPO_4 and NaH_2PO_4 form additional compounds with H_2O_2 . Therefore, the first break in the curve may be due to the stabilising effect given by phosphate ions. Secondly on further addition of phosphate ions the formation of addition compound with H_2O_2 takes place and as it is formed, it confers stability to H_2O_2 and the second abrupt break is obtained. Since the addition compound with H_2O_2 is formed, the further addition of phosphate ions does not show any effect and the curve levels off.

Effect of KH_2PO_4 : In the case of this electrolyte a smooth curve in the Fig. 4 is obtained. The catalytic activity of the suspension decreases with increase in the addition of phosphate ions. But in this case the equivalent amounts of phosphate ions are more effective than in Na_2HPO_4 . It can be explained on the basis that KH_2PO_4 is slightly acidic and H_2O_2 is more stable in acidic solutions.

Mechanism involved in the catalytic decomposition of H_2O_2 . Following the studies of the catalytic decomposition of H_2O_2 with some colloidal metals and hydrous oxides, Weiss²¹ proposed an electron transfer between heterogeneous catalyst and hydrogen peroxide, viz.,

It indicates that in the decomposition of H_2O_2 initial step is the breaking of O—O bond and this has been supported by the investigations of Urey, Dawsey and Rice²². The latter steps which were first suggested by Haber and Willstatter²³ are

Hence the chain of the reaction is started through OH radical.

The interaction of the reacting molecules in the case of heterogeneously catalysed reaction such as in the present case takes place owing, in all probability, to the formation of an intermediate compound i.e. adsorption complex which is more reactive because of its highly unstable and strained state.

Therefore, in the decomposition of H_2O_2 catalysed by hydrous oxides, the initial process is the adsorption of the catalyst. The equation for adsorption isotherm is

$$\frac{x}{m} = KCl^n$$

18. Fischer, *Pharm. Zentr.*, 1907, 48, 57.

19. Quiesser, *Germ. Pat.*, 1919, 321, 616.

20. Menzel and Gabler, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1928, 177, 187.

21. J. Weiss, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1935, 31, 1547-57.

22. Urey, Dawsey and Rice, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 1971.

23. Haber and Willstatter, *Ber.*, 1931, 64, 2844.

where $\frac{x}{m}$ is the amount adsorbed per gm. C the concentration of adsorbate in equilibrium.

$n > 1$ but it changes with the varying concentration of adsorbate and the value of $1/n$ tends to zero on increasing the concentration of the adsorbate. Hence in heterogeneously catalysed reactions²⁴ where adsorption plays an important role, the order of a chemical reaction is likely to change with the varying concentration. Therefore, the calculation of the second order in the case of higher electrolyte concentration is confirmed from the above fact.

Yadav and Ghosh²⁵ have shown the catalytic activity of hydrous bismuth oxide due to formation of quadrivalent Bi(IV) which is reduced to the trivalent state on further reacting with H₂O₂. In the light of their work a similar mechanism could be given for the decomposition of H₂O₂ by hydrous bismuth oxide. The reaction could be represented by the following equations:

(III)

(IV) Unstable

The reaction is started through OH radical,

The higher valent Bi (iv) is reduced to its trivalent state, when it further reacts with H₂O₂,

Although the bismuth oxide is hydrate one, and H₂O should also be included in the equations, but it would not change the mechanism.

It seems quite possible from the above mechanism that hydrous bismuth oxide acts as catalyst for the decomposition of H₂O₂. The preliminary nature of the curves of the electrolyte effects on the catalytic surface resemble with the adsorption isotherm, so the explanation given for this seems to be consistent with the fact that the electrolytes cover up the catalyst surface and reduce its activity.

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25. R. R. Yadav and S. Ghosh, *Z. Physical Chem.*, 1963, 224, (5-6), 289-92.